

AN ORIGINAL APPROACH BASED ON A MODIFIED HALPIN-TSAI MODEL TO INVESTIGATE THE MORPHOLOGY OF SEPIOLITE FILLED THERMOSETS

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1 Introduction

In recent years, nanoclays have attracted great interest [1,2] as they potentially permit significant mechanical properties enhancement at low filler content. Furthermore, they can exhibit added multifunctionality such as flammability resistance, thermal stability [3] and permeability gas barrier properties [4,5]. Since the initial successful development of layered silicate nylon nanocomposites by Toyota team [6], there has been great interest in layered silicate polymer nanocomposites in both academic and industrial research. The most widely used layered silicates in nanocomposites are based on montmorillonites which are composed of extremely thin (~1 nm) platelets with large surface areas and high aspect ratios. These platelets present a very high elastic modulus (within the range 178-265 GPa [7]) compared to that of the polymer matrix. To obtain nanocomposites with enhanced properties comparing to conventional composites, the natural MMT has to be organically modified [8, 9] by a quaternary ammonium salt bearing long carbon chains. Hence, the dispersion of the clay platelets is improved and exfoliated structures can occur. The reinforcement effect of silicate layers strongly depends on the degree of dispersion of the platelets and the structure of the nanocomposite [10]. Recently, sepiolite that is a needle-like shaped clay has been incorporated in polymer matrix to increase its mechanical properties [11-13]. The development of nanocomposites, as pointed out by Brune and Bicerano [14], requires a better understanding of the structure-properties relationship and the ability to make predictions using adapted micromechanical models. Recently, Halpin-Tsai model was used to evaluate the properties of montmorillonite based

nanocomposites [15]. The mechanical behaviour of polymer/clay 'ideal' nanocomposites can be predicted rather well with these models. But, due to the inherent complexity of 'real' nanocomposite structure, it is inevitable that discrepancies occur [16,17]. Moreover, to our knowledge, there are very few works dealing with the viscoelastic properties of sepiolite filled thermosets and also with the correlation between mechanical properties (especially stiffness and damping factor) with the morphology of the nanocomposite. This presentation deals with the study of the reinforcing effect of sepiolite clay mineral dispersed in epoxy vinyl ester (VE) matrix. Elastic modulus were measured by a vibration analysis and compared with those obtained by adapted homogenization models based on Halpin Tsai homogenization models. This allowed to conclude on the microstructure of our nanocomposites (particularly on the dispersion of the fillers).

2 Experimental part

2.1 Materials

The clay material used was a sepiolite Pangel® S9 ('Sep'), supplied from Tolsa (fig.1 and 2). The epoxy vinyl ester (VE) resin used as the matrix was Ashland Derakane® Momentum™ 411-350 ('Mom'). The curing system was composed of a methyl ethyl ketone peroxide catalyzed by a cobalt naphthenate salt (3% in styrene).

2.2 Processing

Suspensions of sepiolite (from 1.25 to 6.25wt%) in resin were mechanically stirred and ultrasonically mixed. The curing system used was composed of 1.5 phr of methyl ethyl ketone peroxide and 0.30 phr of

cobalt naphthenate (3% in styrene). Mixtures were cast into silicone moulds to form 250*80*12 mm blocks. The blocks were then cured for 8 hours at 100°C.

Fig.1. SEM micrography of sepiolite Pangel S9.

For the designation of the samples, for example, Mom1.25Sep means Momentum resin filled with 1.25 wt% of sepiolite.

2.3 Morphology

SEM micrographs were obtained using an environmental scanning electron microscope (FEI Quanta SEM) equipped with a scanning transmission electron microscopy detector (STEM).

Fig.2. sepiolite structure.

2.4 Modal Analysis

Modal analysis is currently used to determine the inherent dynamic characteristics of a structure using its own frequencies, damping factor and mode shapes[18]. The main advantages of modal analysis are: (i) it is a rapid and non-expensive method, (ii) experiments can be performed on non-standardized specimen, (iii) the method is not destructive and specimen can be recovered at the end of the test and finally (iv) a wide band of frequencies is covered. More recently, it has been used to determine the viscoelastic properties of composite materials, especially the influence of fibre length and orientation on the damping and stiffness of polymer composite reinforced with glass fibers [19,20]. Avila et al. [21] showed that the dispersion of nanoclays in fibre glass/epoxy laminates improves the damping ratio. Moreover, the addition of organoclays to fibre reinforced vinylester composites improves significantly the internal damping of the hybrids, as shown by Chandradass et al. [22].

Modal analysis has been used here to determine the elastic modulus of our composite materials. The experimental setup used simulates free boundary conditions by supporting the sample with soft suspensions (Fig.3). The dynamic excitation was provided by an impact hammer. The response was registered by an accelerometer. The excitation and response were fed into the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) analyzer which computed the natural frequencies from the frequency response function (FRF). The natural frequencies of the sample were given by a series of peaks in the frequency response curve (Fig. 4). The MODAN software, developed by FEMTO-ST lab (Université de Franche-Comté) was used to extract natural frequencies and damping ratio from the frequency function response. A finite element model of each sample correlated with the modal analysis was used to identify the elastic modulus of the material.

Fig.3. Modal analysis measurement set-up with hammer excitation.

Fig.4. Example of the frequency response function (FRF) and corresponding mode shapes.

2.5 Modeling using modified Halpin-Tsai model

Elastic modulus (E_c) were calculated for each formulation using a modified Halpin-Tsai model [17], based on several hypothesis: (i) a random distribution of sepiolites, (ii) a linear, elastic and isotropic mechanical behavior of the matrix and sepiolite, and (iii) a perfect interface between matrix and sepiolite fibers. Moreover, the calculation was performed considering a needle of sepiolite as a cylinder with a length L and a diameter d . The calculation of E_c is given by van Es [23]:

$$E_c = 0.816 E_{c//} + 0.184 E_{c\perp}$$

where $E_{c//}$ and $E_{c\perp}$ are the longitudinal and the transverse elastic modulus, respectively.

$$E_{c//} = \frac{1 + \eta_{//} \zeta_{//} \phi_r}{1 - \eta_{//} \phi_r} E_m$$

where ϕ_r and E_m are the volume fraction of sepiolite, and the elastic modulus of the matrix, respectively.

And $\eta_{//}$ is given by:

$$\eta_{//} = \frac{\frac{E_r}{E_m} - 1}{\frac{E_r}{E_m} + \zeta_{//}}$$

and $\zeta_{//}$, the shape parameter in the length direction is given by:

$$\zeta_{//} = 2 \frac{L}{d}$$

E_r is the elastic modulus of the sepiolite needles.

And, $E_{c\perp}$ is given by :

$$E_{c\perp} = \frac{1 + \eta_{\perp} \zeta_{\perp} \phi_r}{1 - \eta_{\perp} \phi_r} E_m$$

where η_{\perp} and ζ_{\perp} (the shape parameter in the transverse) direction are given by:

$$\eta_{\perp} = \frac{\frac{E_r}{E_m} - 1}{\frac{E_r}{E_m} + \zeta_{\perp}}$$

$$\zeta_{\perp} = 2$$

The value of ζ_{\perp} is explained elsewhere [15].

The elastic modulus of the matrix is $E_m=3.22\text{GPa}$. The elastic modulus of the sepiolite has been evaluated elsewhere as $E_r=200\text{GPa}$ [11]. The shape parameter $\zeta_{//}$ usually ranges between 20 and 260 [24] with an average at 54[11].

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Microstructure

The SEM microstructure of the sepiolite filled epoxy vinyl ester resins are given in Fig.5 and clearly evidence the presence of agglomerates of sepiolite needles. All the needles are not individualized.

Fig. 5. SEM micrographs of the sepiolite filled VE resins; from the top to the bottom: Mom1.25Sep, Mom3.75Sep and Mom6.25Sep.

3.2 Elastic modulus by modal analysis

The stiffness of sepiolite filled composites are reported in Table 1. The incorporation of sepiolite in VE resins tends to increase the stiffness of the material. And Table 1 shows a relatively low improvement. Indeed, the highest stiffness is obtained for the Mom5.00Sep ($E=4.23\text{GPa}$) and corresponds to an increase in stiffness of approximately 30%. Actually, these improvements are consistent with the limited literature available on the subject [12]. Table 2 gives the glass transition temperature (T_g) obtained with the maximum $\tan\delta$ measured by DMTA. The glass transition temperatures of the nanocomposites increase with the amount of sepiolite meaning either that the crosslinking density is increased by the addition of sepiolite, or that polymer chains are adsorbed at the surface of sepiolite thus decreasing their mobility.

Table 1: Stiffness of the sepiolite filled VE

Formulation	E (GPa)	
Mom	3.22 ± 0.05	
Mom1.25Sep	3.53 ± 0.05	+ 9.63%
Mom2.50Sep	3.85 ± 0.06	+ 19.56%
Mom3.75Sep	4.15 ± 0.05	+ 28.88 %
Mom5.00Sep	4.23 ± 0.08	+ 31.37 %
Mom6.25Sep	4.05 ± 0.05	+ 25.78%

Table 2: T_g of sepiolite filled VE

Formulation	T_g (°C)
Mom	118.5
Mom1.25Sep	119.3
Mom2.50Sep	118.6
Mom3.75Sep	120.0
Mom5.00Sep	122.1
Mom6.25Sep	122.8

3.3 Modified Halpin-Tsai model

For all the formulations, the elastic modulus were calculated using the model described in § 2.5. The obtained values of E_c were compared to the experimental one (given in Table1) and an effective aspect ratio for sepiolite ($\xi_{//}$) was determined by backcalculation (Table 3). Values of $\xi_{//}$ obtained by backcalculation are varying between 11.3 for the high amounts of sepiolite (6.25 wt%) and 30.5 for low amounts (2.50 wt%). These values are 2 to 5 times lower than that given by Bilotti [11,24] (assuming that the real average aspect ratio of a sepiolite fiber is equal to 54). If we assume that owing to our processing (explained in § 2.2) needles were not broken during the process, it could mean that needles have a tendency to associate into bundles, as shown in Fig 5. An average number of fibers by bundles N_a can be calculated and is given in Table 3. Low values of N_a indicate a good processing efficiency for the composite manufacturing. And as expected, the higher the amount of sepiolite, the lower the efficiency of the process. In our sepiolite-based VE thermosets, bundles may contain 1, 2, 3 or 4 needles (as shown in Fig.5). What is the distribution of the bundles in our materials? To answer this question, we have to answer first if there is a limit for the volume fraction of individualized sepiolite fibers (ϕ_1 , for $N=1$).

Table 3: backcalculation giving $\xi_{//}=2L/d$ and N

Formulation	Calculated $\xi_{//}=2L/d$	N_a
Mom1.25Sep	30.2	1.8
Mom2.50Sep	30.5	1.8
Mom3.75Sep	29.2	1.8
Mom5.00Sep	20.9	2.6
Mom6.25Sep	11.3	4.8

Fig.5. Schematic representation of the sepiolite needle bundles with $N=1, 2, 3$ and 4 .

We assume that the volume fraction of individualized sepiolite fibers (ϕ_1 , for $N=1$) is limited by an upper bound ϕ_{max} , that is the ratio between the volume of a sepiolite needle ($\pi d^2 L/4$) on the cube of the highest dimension (L^3).

Hence, ϕ_1 is given by [16]:

$$\phi_1 < \phi_{max} = \frac{\pi d^2 L}{4L^3} = \frac{\pi}{\zeta_{//}^2} = 0.107\%$$

This condition is considered to be very restrictive and is represented in Fig.6 that shows the volume around each individualized needles.

τ_1 is defined as the rate of individualized sepiolite fibers :

$$\tau_1 = \frac{\phi_1}{\phi_r}$$

And τ_{1max} is the theoretical maximum rate of individualized sepiolite fibers (under the hypothesis mentioned below):

$$\tau_1 < \tau_{1max} = \frac{\pi d^2 L}{4L^3 \phi_r} = \frac{\pi}{\zeta_{//}^2 \phi_r}$$

Fig.6. schematic representation of the individualized sepiolite needles in their limited volume.

Fig.7. $\tau_{1 \max}$ versus ϕ_r .

Hence, Fig.7 confirms that there is low amount of individualized fibers in the composite, especially for high volume fraction of sepiolites. Indeed, the maximum value of individualized needles is almost 20 % for 1.25 wt% of sepiolite.

A new modeling of E_c (based on Halpin Tsai and given in § 2.5) is then proposed assuming that the maximum amount of individualized sepiolite ($\tau_{1 \max}$) is reached and that among the remaining fraction of needles, the maximum amount of needles under bundles of two is also reached ($\tau_{2 \max}$), and that among the remaining fraction of needles, the maximum amount of needles under bundles of three is also reached ($\tau_{3 \max}$) until there is no more needles available. Fig. 8 is a schematic representation of this modeling.

The general expression giving the maximum amount of bundles of N needles ($\tau_{N \max}$) is:

$$\tau_{N \max} = \frac{\pi N^2}{\zeta_{//}^2 \phi_r}$$

where $\zeta_{//}$ is equal to 54.

Fig.8. Schematic representation of the modeling used to evaluate E_c of the sepiolite-VE composites.

Finally, by taking these assumptions into account, a new calculation of E_c is performed and shown in Fig. 9. Hence, it is shown that calculated values of the elastic modulus are close to the experimental ones for all the formulations except for 6.25% of sepiolite (Fig. 9). Moreover, for Mom2.50Sep and Mom3.75Sep, the experimental values of E_c are higher than the calculated ones. This confirms that our hypothesis on the amount of individualized needles is probably too restrictive and that for those two formulations the number of individualized needles is probably higher than 6.5 and 4.7 % for Mom3.75Sep and Mom5.00Sep, respectively (as shown in Fig.7).

Fig.9. Elastic modulus E_c measured by modal analysis (■) and calculated with modified Halpin-Tsai model (○).

The gap between calculated and experimental modulus permits to evaluate (by backcalculation) the average number of needles per bundle and, by using τ_1 ($I = 1, 2, 3, 4$) to determine the distribution between individualized, 2, 3 or 4 associated needles (Table 4).

Table 4. Distribution of the sepiolite needles in bundles.

Formulation	N	ϕ_N (%)	E_c (%)	N_a
Mom1.25Sep	1	19.52	26.28	1.83
	2	78.08	71.94	
	3	2.40	1.78	
Mom2.5Sep	1	9.69	15.00	2.42
	2	38.76	41.05	
	3	51.55	43.95	
Mom3.75Sep	1	6.41	10.53	2.72
	2	25.66	28.83	
	3	57.73	52.39	
	4	10.20	8.24	
Mom5.00Sep	1	4.78	8.24	3.04
	2	19.11	22.55	
	3	42.99	40.97	
	4	33.13	28.24	
Mom6.25Sep	1	3.79	6.73	3.24
	2	15.17	18.43	
	3	34.14	33.50	
	4	46.89	41.34	

It is clear that formulation for which the process was optimized (*i.e.* the highest rate of individualized sepiolite needles is attained) is the Mom1.25Sep.

Moreover, Table 4 reveals that the contribution to the elastic modulus of individualized needles dramatically decreases when the volume fraction of sepiolite increases.

To conclude, a modified Halpin-Tsai model was successfully used to prove that sepiolite fibers -in a VE matrix- are assembled into bundles, limiting the stiffness improvement of the nanocomposite.

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